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📘 Model Fit Statistics

	Export CSV	Export Excel									
Model	n_profiles	LogLik	AIC	BIC	Entropy	prob_min	prob_max	n_min	n_max	BLRT_val	BLRT_p
1	1	-7482.86	15061.72	15255.2	1	1	1	1	1		
1	2	-5939	12024.01	12318.25	0.95	0.98	0.99	0.38	0.62		
1	3	-5500.99	11197.97	11592.98	0.94	0.97	0.98	0.19	0.46		
1	4	-5085.62	10417.24	10913.01	0.97	0.97	0.99	0.16	0.45		
1	5	-4977	10250.01	10846.55	0.96	0.94	0.99	0.12	0.36		
1	6	-5005.05	10356.1	11053.41	0.96	0.95	0.99	0.03	0.38		

Note:

- Model selection: The selected LPA model defines the variance–covariance structure across profiles and influences interpretability and classification quality.
- Model 1: Equal variances, covariances fixed to zero (most parsimonious).
- Model 2: Varying variances, covariances fixed to zero (allows different variability).
- Model 3: Equal variances and covariances across profiles.
- Model 6: Varying variances and covariances (most flexible, higher risk of overfitting).
- BIC / AIC: Lower values indicate better relative model fit.
- Entropy: Classification accuracy (values close to 1 indicate clear profiles).
- prob_min / prob_max: Minimum and maximum average posterior probabilities for assigned profiles.
- n_min / n_max: Proportion of the sample in the smallest and largest profiles.
- BLRT: Significant results favor the k-profile model over the k–1 model.

BIC Comparison Across Models

Model 1

AIC Comparison Across Models

Model 1

Entropy Comparison Across Models

Model 1

Min Class Size Comparison Across Models

Model 1